

Integrating Uncertainty into U-Net Robustness Evaluation under Natural MRI Alterations: Application to Kidney Segmentation

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Abstract. The adoption of deep learning (DL) for medical image segmentation in clinical practice is limited by interpretability issues and sensitivity to out-of-distribution data. Robust models that maintain stable accuracy while offering reliable uncertainty estimates in the presence of data variations should be required. We propose a framework to evaluate the robustness of U-Net-based segmentation on a kidney MRI dataset, simulating common abdominal MRI distortions. Robustness is assessed using a novel metric that evaluates both the network’s accuracy stability and uncertainty reliability. The results show that, while segmentation accuracy remains stable across alterations, uncertainty is more sensitive to these changes. This suggests that capturing also uncertainty offers a more comprehensive assessment of DL models than traditional accuracy-focused frameworks.

Keywords: Segmentation · Uncertainty · Robustness · Kidney MRI

1 Introduction

Deep learning (DL) has revolutionized medical image segmentation, but its adoption in clinics is limited due to the lack of transparency. To overcome this, quantifying uncertainty in model predictions can help clinicians identify unreliable model outputs [7]. Moreover, DL models are sensitive to input data variations, e.g., differences in imaging protocols, equipment and patient movement, which leads to out-of-distribution (OOD) data and performance degradation when models trained on uniform data encounter real-world perturbations, hindering their generalizability [1]. Assessing and improving model robustness in terms of stable performance despite data variations is crucial for reliable medical outcomes [5]. Additionally, robustness evaluation should consider uncertainty

estimation, as a robust model must provide both accurate outputs and reliable uncertainty estimates under varying conditions [3]. Essbai *et al.* [3] proposed a framework to assess the robustness of classifiers to input alterations, considering both accuracy and uncertainty. However, this framework has not yet been tested neither for segmentation tasks or medical datasets. In this study, we evaluate the robustness of U-Net models for renal MRI segmentation against common MRI distortions, adapting the metrics of [3] to assess both segmentation accuracy and uncertainty, considering various uncertainty quantification approaches.

2 Methods

2.1 MRI Dataset and Natural MRI Alterations

A publicly available dataset of T2-weighted coronal MRI scans of the kidney of 60 subjects, 30 with chronic kidney disease (CKD) and 30 healthy controls (HC), was used [2]. 50 subjects (25 CKD and 25 HC) were used during training (80% training, 20% validation), while the remaining 10 subjects (5 CKD, 5 HC) were kept separate for testing. Manually segmented kidney masks were provided as ground truth (GT). Preprocessing followed the pipeline described in [2].

OOD data were simulated by applying MRI-specific transformations to the test data using TorchIo [6], including spatial (Affine, Anisotropy) and intensity (Motion artifacts, Ghosting, Bias Field, Blurring, Noise, Gamma) transformations. Each of them was applied 20 times, with magnitudes T_j ($j = 1, \dots, 20$) randomly sampled within a range set to mimic actual MRI artifacts, based on the authors’ expertise.

2.2 DL-based Segmentation and Uncertainty Estimation

A 2D U-Net was used for kidney segmentation, according to the architecture of Daniel *et al.* [2]. Predictive uncertainty was estimated through Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD) [4] and Test-Time Augmentation (TTA) [8].

Four stochastic networks were trained: MCD and TTA with the Dice Loss, and MCD_{PLUS} and TTA_{PLUS} with the Dice Plus Loss [9], which improves model calibration. Data augmentation was applied during training; a learning rate of 10^{-4} , 100 epochs, a batch size of 16, and a dropout rate of 0.25 were adopted.

During inference, 50 predictions were obtained for each test image, which were then pixel-wise averaged and binarized to generate the mean prediction (MP) masks. Predictive uncertainty for each pixel was computed as in [7].

2.3 Robustness Evaluation

The models were evaluated in terms of robustness against data transformations, separately for CKD and HC subjects. Two metrics were adapted from Essbai *et al.* [3] to assess robustness specifically for segmentation tasks.

Robustness (*rob*). It quantifies the model’s ability to maintain predictive accuracy on altered data. A low value indicates a decrease in model’s accuracy,

suggesting sensitivity to transformations and instability. Robustness against a transformation type T was calculated by considering the transformation level probability π_{T_j} , the tolerance to accuracy decrease $tol(Dice^{T_j}, \theta)$, and the penalization for unacceptable accuracy $dep(Dice^{T_j}, \theta)$:

$$rob^T = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{20} [tol(Dice^{T_j}, \theta) - dep(Dice^{T_j}, \theta)] \pi_{T_j} + \frac{1}{2}. \quad (1)$$

θ is the minimum accepted accuracy threshold, set to 0.7, and $\pi_{T_j} = \frac{1}{20}$ as each T_j ($j = 1, \dots, 20$) was sampled randomly from the range of each transformation. tol and dep functions were defined as in Essbai *et al.* [3], using the *Dice* coefficient as the quality metric in their *Def. 6* and *Def. 7*.

Augmented robustness (rob_{Aug}). It assesses both accuracy and uncertainty, quantifying the model’s ability to provide accurate results along with reliable confidence estimates under altered inputs. Model accuracy was evaluated using *Dice*, and the goodness of uncertainty estimation was assessed by the incorrect-uncertain ratio (RIU) [7], which captures the proportion of incorrect and uncertain pixels to total incorrect pixels. A high RIU suggests that the model effectively identifies uncertain areas where predictions are likely incorrect. The uncertainty threshold for distinguishing certain and uncertain pixels was experimentally set to 0.05 in our application. The effectiveness metric (eff) was defined as:

$$eff = 2 Dice \frac{RIU}{RIU + 1}. \quad (2)$$

Augmented robustness (rob_{Aug}) was then computed as:

$$rob_{Aug}^T = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^{20} [tol(eff^{T_j}, \beta) - dep(eff^{T_j}, \beta)] \pi_{T_j} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (3)$$

using eff as metric in tol and dep functions. β is the minimum accepted effectiveness threshold, set to 0.16 following the same criterion as in [3].

3 Results

Figure 1 shows rob and rob_{Aug} results on the augmented test set for CKD and HC subjects, for each transformation type. rob consistently showed values above 0.7 for all alterations and methods, with no appreciable differences between CKD and HC subjects. All models experienced a decrease in rob_{Aug} compared to rob for CKD subjects. In HC subjects, this was only observed for MCD. MCD_{PLUS} and TTA_{PLUS} outperformed MCD and TTA, respectively, with MCD showing the lowest rob_{Aug} values, as illustrated in Figure 2 where an image of a CKD patient corrupted with a Bias Field artifact is reported. For MCD, uncertainty was concentrated along the kidney contour and failed to highlight misclassified regions, while the other models successfully identified incorrectly classified pixels. Lower rob_{Aug} values were observed for the Bias Field artifact, while the highest performance was achieved with Affine transformations.

Fig. 1. Medians and interquartile ranges of rob (a,b) and rob_{Aug} (c,d) for CKD (a,c) and HC (b,d) subjects.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

All approaches demonstrated a high degree of rob across the various input alterations, indicating that accuracy remains acceptable in the presence of these changes. However, models experienced a decline in rob_{Aug} , particularly in CKD patients, whose anatomy is inherently more complex and variable. MCD exhibited the poorest performance, making it unsuitable for uncertainty assessment. In contrast, models trained with the Dice Plus Loss performed better, providing a trustworthy alert on misclassified regions. Across the different data transformations, Bias Field distortions resulted in lower rob and rob_{Aug} values. On the other hand, Affine transformations resulted in more robust uncertainty estimates across all models, probably due to their similarity to the distortions used during the augmentation of training data. This suggests that including transformations similar to those encountered in real-world scenarios during training may improve segmentation performance.

These results are limited by the small size and relatively simple nature of the dataset, and should be tested on more challenging data. Kidneys are anatomically well-defined structures, which makes segmentation relatively easier compared to more complex or pathological structures, such as kidney cysts or tumors. Therefore, these findings should be tested on more challenging datasets. Furthermore, robustness values are highly dependent on the selected thresholds, and proper evaluation is required to determine optimal threshold settings. Despite these limitations, the results highlight the importance of robustness metrics that also take into account the reliability of uncertainty estimates.

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Fig. 2. GT (yellow line) and MP (red line) kidney contours in a representative CKD subject, together with the uncertainty map for each uncertainty quantification method.

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Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare.

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